

Abstract for ESA Living Planet Symposium 2019

Session: A.3 Biosphere

Title: Early detection of forest disease outbreaks from Sentinel-2 imagery by utilizing airborne hyperspectral data.

Authors: Martijn Vermeer, Maria Jozefiak, Christina Aas*, Vasco Mantas+, Nicolas Lewyckyj†

*: Science [&] Technology AS, www.stcorp.no, corresponding author: vermeer@stcorp.no

+: University of Coimbra, www.uc.pt/en, co-author: vasco.mantas@gmail.com

†: VITO NV, www.vito.be/en, co-author: Nicolas.lewyckyj@vito.be

Intro/background:

The global forest economy is subject to a number of threats to its production value. Forest disease outbreaks become more frequent due to globalisation and climate change - they are difficult to contain and mitigate. According to FAO, in the period 1980-2002 more than 52 mill. hectares of forest in 37 countries were damaged by pests. The Pine Wilt Nematode is estimated, due to predictions in changing climate, to have the potential to spread to 34% of Europe by 2030. Forest fires are escalating in severity, and costs due to climate change are increasing. Europe lost in 2017 three times as large an area to forest fires than during the period 2008-2016 in total. The forest fires cost Portugal alone more than 200 mill. EUR and killed at least 66 people in 2017. These forest threats require accurate, precise and frequent information for monitoring tree stand status and planning any relevant mitigation actions. Sentinel-2 becoming operational in 2015, and the impressive results of deep learning techniques, served as an ideal starting point for the automated forest monitoring service Silvisense. Silvisense provides forest owners with a digital service to automatically monitor and report the state of forest inventory.

Challenge:

Early symptoms of forest disease are only reflected by small changes in the spectral reflectance, which are difficult to detect from Sentinel-2 imagery alone. Such minor variations in the spectral reflectance could be detected from airborne hyperspectral data, increasing the capacity to reveal disease outbreaks at an earlier stage.

Goal:

This forms the basis of the European Commission H2020 project FOCUS (Forest Operational monitoring using Copernicus and UAV hyperSpectral data), which aims to improve and extend the Silvisense forest monitoring services by combining multispectral data from Sentinel-2 with hyperspectral data from remotely piloted airborne platforms. The added value of the hyperspectral data particularly lies in the possibility to detect forest diseases at an earlier stage. The focus of this paper will be on the adaption of the Silvisense processing chain for early onset forest disease detection.

Methods:

An initial case study is conducted in Portugal, where outbreaks of the Pine Wilt Disease (PWD) threaten 70% of the forest population. A number of test sites have been selected at different geographical settings. At each site, tree samples are regularly taken for analyses in the lab. Their physical and biochemical variables are measured to find the effects of wilting within the pine needles. Spectral measurements enable to relate wilting to changes in the reflected spectra of the needles. In multiple airborne campaigns all test sites are visited to gather multi and hyperspectral data throughout the season. Aerial campaigns are synchronized with Sentinel-2 overpasses and ground sampling campaigns, such that the data can be related to each other. The resulting datasets

serve to create accurate and high-resolution ground truth data for the parameters linked to PWD. Most importantly, this data can be used as training data for deep learning algorithms for Sentinel-2 image classification. The classified images are further improved by means of Markov smoothing over the temporal dimension. Since Sentinel-2 has a revisit time of 5 days, there is a lot to gain by exploiting temporal information. The actual mapping of disease outbreaks is based on change detection between classified images from different times. In order to efficiently process these large data volumes a processing framework is designed. One of the main advantages is, that it allows to reuse previously computed results from different components. This processing framework is part of the Silvisense forest monitoring service, in which the resulting products of the FOCUS project are implemented.

Preliminary results:

From the ground sampling and airborne campaigns already conducted within the FOCUS project, significant differences have been found between the reflected spectra of healthy and wilting pine needles. Furthermore, these differences can clearly be identified in the collected hyperspectral airborne data. Based on this, it is expected that high quality ground truth data can be created for training the Sentinel-2 image classifier. Ultimately this should make it possible to adapt the Silvisense processing chain for the early detection of PWD. This case study furthermore forms a proof of concept for the detection of similar symptoms from outbreaks of other forest diseases.